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"AVARIS NET" CRISIS AND EMERGENCY MANAGEMENT OF HEALTH SERVICES

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ABSTRACT

Through this work we had created a system that supports management of rescue teams and health services during a major disaster. The system can be installed in the disaster area using its own infrastructure (telecommunications and power). It mainly consists of a central/control station which is installed in the area control center, the rescuers units (portable android devices/smart phones 4-5 inch screens or android watches), the ambulance vehicles units (tablet android devices 7 inch screen) and the telemedicine units that can be used in order to support the evaluation at the casualties clearing station. These are the first steps in order to create an electronic management system that can be used as an additional tool to support the already existing disaster management plans/framework as well as for training purposes.

METHODOLOGY

Management of Health Services during crisis or disasters is the major field of interest of this work. According to the World Health Organisation report, over the years 2001-2010, an average of 700 disasters (flood earthquakes etc.) is reported every year. Annually, an estimated 270 million people were affected and more than 130,000 were killed [1]. However, in the chaos of a disaster such effective and efficient response is not easy. Several issues can arise because of problems in communications (both access and core networks), decision-making protocols and efficiency, and coordination in dispatching of units. In addition the response to such events can be seriously improved through additional electronic support, continuous training of personnel and regular professional exercises [2].

Following the above needs, the goal of this work is to create an electronic management system that can be integrated in the already existing crisis response plans/framework [3], [4] and support management of rescue teams and health services provision during a major disaster.

The system consists of (Figure 1):

1. Central/control station (Windows computer installed in the local area control center)
2. The rescuers units (android smartphone/watches up to 4-5 inches)
3. The ambulance vehicles units (tablet android devices with 7-8 inches screen)
4. The emergency telemedicine units [5] that can be used to support the evaluation of victims at the casualties clearing station.

The central station has the control of all the rescuers and ambulance vehicles in the disaster area. From there the chief of operations is able to have an overview of the rescuers, victims and Ambulances in order to direct the operations. An overview of the system architecture and information flow is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Crisis Management System Architecture

System's Main Characteristics:

1. Live monitoring of victims and their evaluation status. (Black, yellow, red, green), estimated age, sex. After the evaluation each victim is marked with a card that has a QRcode or an NFC tag (Figure 3 is showing the procedure followed by the rescuers)
2. Monitoring of rescuers in the area and their status (available or not) (Figure 2)
3. Monitoring of ambulance vehicles entering the area and their status (type, occupied or not) (Figure 2)
4. Everything is traced using Global Positioning System and presented on an area map at the control station (Figure 2)
5. Real time monitoring of selected victims from the casualties clearing station through the telemedicine units (ECG 3-12 leads and parameters like SpO2 etc.) [5]
6. All information can be transferred to a central control center, through satellite or 3G networks if available. (Figure 1)

Figure 2: Area monitoring screen - central station unit

EVALUATION

After finishing the technical evaluation in the lab. The system was initially tested/evaluated through a Major Incidents Prehospital Management Course, March 29-31 2014. This was a training course organised by the Cyprus Emergency and Prehospital Association (<http://www.ksepa-cyprus.org/>).

The research team had setup the crisis management system and the emergency telemedicine system. Both systems were applied at the last day of the course where two exercises took place.

Both exercises were in collaboration with the Cyprus Emergency and Prehospital Association and the Special Fire and Rescue Unit EMAK.

1. The scenario of the first exercise was for a major explosion in the area of fuel refineries in Larnaca Cyprus.
2. The scenario of the second exercise was for a major earthquake with several victims. An overview of the earthquake disaster area is shown in figure 4. The area was divided according to the procedures followed by the rescuers during a major disaster. The victims and rescuers localisation system was used in the hot zone area, while the telemedicine unit was installed in the casualties clearing (1st evaluation) station

Figure 4: Overview of the earthquake area defined for the disaster professional exercise

Figure 3: Procedure followed by the rescuers during initial victim treatment and evaluation

CONCLUSIONS

These are the initial steps in order to create an electronic management system for major disasters. The system was initially tested in a professional exercise for major disasters. Initial results and feedback from rescuers were very promising while the majority of the users indicated that the use of such a system can help them and support better information flow, communication and control between all the teams working in a major disaster area.

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